

Studies on Outer-sphere Association of some Diamminebis(1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea)cobalt(III) Complexes

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Conductometric studies of the equilibria : $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]^{3+} + \text{X}^- \rightleftharpoons \{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2\text{X}]^{2+} + [\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]^{3+} + \text{X}^- \rightleftharpoons \{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2\text{X}]^{2+}$ (AMUH = 1-amidino-*O*-methylurea, AEUH = 1-amidino-*O*-ethylurea; X = Cl, Br, I and 0.5 SO_4) have been carried out in aqueous solution at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$. The stability constants of the outer-sphere association of the complexes have been calculated following the method of Jenkins and Monk and are found to follow the order : (a) $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^-$ and (b) AMUH > AEUH. Using Bjerrum equation and Stoke's law, the respective sizes of the ion-pairs have been evaluated and compared.

The outer-sphere ion-association of some cobalt(III) complex ions with various anions have been investigated conductometrically¹⁻⁶ and spectrophotometrically⁷. Recently, Yokoyama and co-workers⁸ studied conductometrically the ion-pair formation of tris(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) ions with monovalent anions in the temperatures range $0-50^\circ$. So far less work has been done on outer-sphere ion-association of cobalt(III) complexes containing 1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea as primary ligand. In the present study, electrical conductivities of aqueous solutions of chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate of diamminebis(1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea)cobalt(III) have been measured at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and the corresponding outer-sphere ion-association constants have been evaluated. Using Bjerrum equation and Stoke's law, the respective sizes of the ion-pairs have also been evaluated and compared.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of association constant : Equivalent conductivities (Λ_{exp}) of the complexes have been measured at different concentrations in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The limiting equivalent conductivities (Λ°) of the complexes were determined by Onsager's method of extrapolation⁹ and whence Λ_1 , the limiting conductivity of the complex cation was available (Table 1. Fig. 1). The relation between

the equivalent conductivity and the concentration (C , equivalent/dm³) was analysed according to the limiting equation of Onsager⁹,

$$\Lambda = \Lambda^\circ - b\sqrt{C} \quad (1)$$

where b is the theoretical slope. The experimental conductivity plots (Figs. 2 and 3) lie below the theoretical Onsager plot⁹ (drawn according to equation 1) which indicates that outer-sphere association occurs in these complexes.

Fig. 1. Onsager extrapolation : (a) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}_3$, (b) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_3$, (c) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Br}_3$, (d) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_3$, (e) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}_3$ and (f) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Br}_3$.

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE DATA OF DIAMINE-BIS(1-AMIDINO-*O*-ALKYLUREA)COBALT(III) IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 25 ± 0.1°

Compd.	$\Lambda_{\text{appr}}^{\circ}$	$\Lambda_{\text{Oms}}^{\circ}$	$\Lambda_{\text{Cation}}^{\circ}$	$\Lambda_{\text{I}}^{\circ}(\text{Me in})$
I. [Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AMUH) ₂]Cl ₃	138.79	137.16	60.82	
[Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AMUH) ₂]Br ₃	141.74	140.15	62.05	60.85
[Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AMUH) ₂]I ₃	134.69	136.49	59.69	
II [Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AEUH) ₂]Cl ₃	130.46	128.95	52.61	
[Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AEUH) ₂]Br ₃	130.99	129.99	51.89	52.41
[Co(NH ₃) ₂ (AEUH) ₂]I ₃	130.30	129.54	52.74	

Fig. 2. Conductivities of (a) [Co(NH₃)₂(AMUH)₂]Cl₃, (b) [Co(NH₃)₂(AMUH)₂]Br₃ and (c) [Co(NH₃)₂(AMUH)₂]I₃; upper line shows calculated $\Lambda (= \Lambda_{\text{Oms}}^{\circ} - b_c c^{1/2})$ vs $c^{1/2}$ and lower line shows Λ_{exp} vs $c^{1/2}$.

Assuming the ion-pair to be $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AAUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ (AAUH = 1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea; X = Cl, Br or I), the dissociation constant for equilibrium,

$$K = \frac{[\text{X}^-][\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AAUH})_2]^{3+}}{[\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AAUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+}]}$$

$$= \frac{(2 + \alpha)mf_1f_3}{(1 - \alpha)f_2} \quad (3)$$

has been calculated following the method of Jenkins and Monk². In equation (3), α represents the degree

Fig. 3. Conductivities of (a) [Co(NH₃)₂(AMUH)₂]Cl₃, (b) [Co(NH₃)₂(AMUH)₂]Br₃ and (c) [Co(NH₃)₂(AMUH)₂]I₃; upper line shows calculated $\Lambda (= \Lambda_{\text{Oms}}^{\circ} - b_c c^{1/2})$ vs $c^{1/2}$ and lower line shows Λ_{exp} vs $c^{1/2}$.

of dissociation of the ion-pair and f_1 , f_2 and f_3 are the activity coefficient of X^- , $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AAUH})_2]^{3+}$ and $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AAUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ respectively. The activity coefficient f_1 of the ionic species in very dilute solutions has been calculated from the Debye-Hückel equation¹⁰,

$$-\log f_1 = 0.509 Z_1^2 \sqrt{I} \quad (4)$$

where f_1 refers to the activity coefficient of the Z_1 ions. I , the ionic strength is given by

$$I = (1 + \alpha) C \quad (5)$$

where C is the concentration in equivalent per litre.

The experimental solution is taken as a mixture of (i) 3 : 1 valent salt of molar concentration m and (ii) 2 : 1 valent salt of molar concentration $(1 - \alpha)m$, where m is the molar concentration of the salt. The Onsager equations for 3 : 1 and 2 : 1 valent salts of the complexes were set up in the general form, $\Lambda_{\text{expt}} = \Lambda_{\text{ions}}^{\circ} - b\sqrt{I}$, in which the Λ° values for the ion-pairs $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AAUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ were assumed to be equal to two-third that of trivalent ion $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AAUH})_2]^{3+}$ as suggested in the previous studies^{2,3,5,11}

The solvent corrected specific conductivity of the solution is given by²

$$10^3 \kappa = 3\alpha m \Lambda_{31} + 2(1-\alpha) m \Lambda_{21}$$

and equivalent conductivity is given by

$$\Lambda_{\text{expt}} = \Lambda_{31} + 2/3(1-\alpha)\Lambda_{21} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) assume the following general form,

$$\alpha = \frac{\Lambda_{\text{expt}} + A\sqrt{I} - B}{C - D\sqrt{I}} \quad (7)$$

where A , B , C and D are constants depending on the equations for Λ_{31} Λ_{21} . Starting with the values of α as 1 in equation (5) and substituting the corresponding value of \sqrt{I} in equation (7), a truer value of α is obtained, which is again fed into equation (5), and in this way the cycle is repeated till the constant value of α is obtained. The computed values¹² of K_A for diamminebis(1-amidino-*O*-methylurea)cobalt(III) chloride, bromide and iodide, diamminebis(1-amidino-*O*-ethylurea)cobalt(III) chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate complexes are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ASSOCIATION CONSTANT (K_A) OF DIAMMINEBIS(1-AMIDINO-*O*-ALKYLUREA)COBALT(III) COMPLEXES

	Ion-pair	K_A
I	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	47.57
	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Br}\}^{2+}$	45.36
	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}\}^{2+}$	32.59
II	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	43.78
	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Br}\}^{2+}$	30.49
	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{I}\}^{2+}$	23.76
	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{SO}_4\}^+$	18.94×10^2

For the sulphate salt $\Lambda_{\text{O}(\text{O}nsager)}^{\circ}$ was obtained by adding 80.00 for the sulphate ion to the mean limiting conductivity of the cation derived from chloride, bromide and iodide salts, Assuming the equilibrium as

the three Onsager equations for the three types of ions are written as

$$\text{for } [\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]^{3+}, \Lambda_1' = 52.41 - 138.89\sqrt{I}$$

$$\text{SO}_4^{2-}, \Lambda_1'' = 80.00 - 165.89\sqrt{I}$$

$$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{SO}_4\}^+, \Lambda_1''' = 17.47 - 46.29\sqrt{I}$$

where I is the ionic strength and is given by the expression,

$$I = 1/2\{9[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]^{3+} + 4[\text{SO}_4]^{2-} + [\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{SO}_4^{2+}\}$$

$$= 15m - 6x$$

$$= 2.5C - 6x$$

where x is the concentration of the ion-pair. The observed conductivity relates to the calculated conductivity as²

$$\Lambda_1' + \Lambda_1'' - \Lambda_{\text{expt}} = (x/c)(3\Lambda_1' + 2\Lambda_1'' + \Lambda_1''') \quad (9)$$

From equations (8) and (9), the dissociation constant,

$$K = \frac{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]^{3+} [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{SO}_4\}^+]}$$

$$= \frac{(2m-x)(3m-x)f_1f_2}{xf_3}$$

had been obtained. The outer-sphere association constant for diamminebis(1-amidino-*O*-ethylurea)cobalt(III) sulphate is also included in Table 2.

The association constants for diamminebis(1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea)cobalt(III) complexes follow the order :

(i) $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}\}^{2+} > \{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Br}\}^{2+} > \{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}\}^{2+}$, (ii) $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{SO}_4\}^+ > \{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Cl}\}^{2+} > \{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Br}\}^{2+} > \{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{I}\}^{2+}$ and (iii) $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+} > \{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{X}\}^{2+}$

The above trends of association constants for SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- , Br^- and I^- complexes are in agreement with those values of analogous series obtained earlier⁶. It could be explained in terms of solvation concept and hydrogen bonding as explained in earlier work⁶. The drastic increase in the value of association constant of sulphate complex might also be due to large hydrogen bonds between the ammine groups of the inner coordination sphere and the oxyanion of the primary valency. The association constants were also found to increase with decreasing size of the ligand and increasing the charge of the anion forming the ion-pair.

Evaluation of sizes of ion-pairs : From the knowledge of the limiting conductivity of the ions, the ionic radii have been evaluated using Stoke's law¹³,

$$a = \frac{9.16 \times 10^{-7} Z_i}{\Lambda_i^{\circ}} \quad (11)$$

where a is the radius of the i -th ion, Z_i the valency of the i -th ion and Λ_i° the limiting mobility of the i -th ion. The distance of the closest approach of the two ions of an ion-pair is assumed to be equal to the sum of the Stoke's radii of the complex cation and the ion. Expectedly, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]^{3+}$ (5.24 Å is substantially bigger than $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]^{3+}$ (4.52 Å which in turn is bigger than $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ (2.77 Å)².

The sizes of ion-pairs have also been obtained from their association constants by using Bjerrum relationship¹⁴,

$$K_A = 1/K = \frac{4\pi N}{1000} \left[\frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{DkT} \right]^3 Q(b) \quad (12)$$

$$\text{where } b = \frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{aDkT},$$

a being the distance of the closest approach of ion forming the ion-pair. From the experimental association constant K_A , one can calculate the value of $Q(b)$ and from $Q(b)$ value the value of b is obtained from standard table¹⁵. The Stoke's radii of the ion-pairs have been compared with those of Bjerrum distances (Table 3), but unfortunately the two results do not agree well. However, such discrepancies have also been reported by other workers^{2,4,16}. The discrepancy between sizes of ion-pairs as calculated from Stoke's law and Bjerrum equation might be due the difference in interpreting the ion-pair concept. In Stoke's law, the sizes of the strongly hydrated ions are calculated from their mobilities. The sizes of the ion-pair is assumed to be the sum of these solvated cations and anions. In case of Bjerrum, it identifies ion as ion pairs, which are not in physical contact; the pair is counted as an ion-pair as long as $r < q$, where q is the Bjerrum critical distance¹⁸ and r the distance between two ions.

Experimental

Diaminebis(1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea)cobalt(III) chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate complexes were prepared according to ported procedure¹⁷. All the complexes were crystallised at least twice from conductivity water. The purity of the sample was examined by conventional chemical analyses and spectral measurements. The result were in good agreement with the literature values (as shown in parentheses). The percentage composition of the element and water are : (i) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ {Co, 12.35 (12.10)}, N, 29.00 (28.80), Cl, 22.15 (21.80), H₂O, 11.20 (11.12)}; (ii) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \cdot \text{Br}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ {Co, 9.91 (9.80)}, N, 23.38 (23.29), Br, 40.17 (39.95), H₂O, 6.02 (5.99)}; (iii) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \cdot \text{I}_3$, {Co, 8.47 (8.38), N, 20.18 (19.80), I, 53.76 (54.10)}; (iv) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. {Co, 10.94 (10.70)}, N, 25.69 (25.50), Cl, 19.42 (19.30), H₂O, 16.70 (16.37)}; (v) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] \cdot \text{Br}_3$, {Co, 10.10 (9.90)}, N, 29.95 (29.70), Br, 40.12 (40.40)}; (vi) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] \cdot \text{I}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, {Co, 7.70 (7.60)}, N, 17.95 (18.10), I, 50.11 (49.50), H₂O, 4.58 (4.67)} and (vii) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \cdot (\text{SO}_4)_3$, {Co, 11.98 (11.87)}, N, 28.37 (28.10), SO₄, 29.42 (29.00)}. The complexes were then dried at 110° to a constant weight

TABLE 3—IONIC RADII OF CATION/ANION AND ION-PAIRS FOR DIAMMINEBIS(1-AMIDINO-*O*-ALKYLUREA)COBALT(III) COMPLEXES

Cation/Anion/Ion-pair	Radius from Stoke's law (Å)	Radius, from Bjerrum eqn (Å)
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2]^{3+}$	4.52	
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2]^{3+}$	5.24	
Cl^-	1.20	
Br^-	1.18	
I	1.19	
SO_4^{2-}	2.29	
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	5.72	4.87
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \cdot \text{Br}\}^{2+}$	5.70	5.03
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AMUH})_2] \cdot \text{I}\}^{2+}$	5.70	6.17
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	6.44	5.14
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] \cdot \text{Br}\}^{2+}$	6.42	6.40
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] \cdot \text{I}\}^{2+}$	6.43	7.22
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{AEUH})_2] \cdot \text{SO}_4\}^+$	7.53	4.68

The conductivity measurements were made at 1 kHz with a D.D.R. conductivity meter (Systronic 304 after thermal equilibrium in a Haake Mess-technik D8-G thermostat, 25 ± 0.01°). The complete measurements for one solution were accomplished in every case within 5 h after the preparation of

the solution. The observed conductivities were corrected for the conductivity of the solvent and for the minor conductivity change considered due to the decomposition of the complex^{4,5}

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